

Make sustainable changes sustainable

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Statement: *“We wish that politics, funding agencies, and academics can work together to protect our planet and fulfill our duty to perform research in a socially responsible and sustainable way.”*

Performing experimental research has an immense impact on our environment. Recent estimates find that laboratories are responsible for 5.5 million tons of plastic waste every year [1] and they use on average 3–5 times more energy than offices [2]. With the growing awareness about environmental challenges faced by our planet (such as climate change) as well as an increasing number of knowledge resources (e.g. www.mygreenlab.org; www.sustainabilityexchange.ac.uk and many others), more and more scientists turn to various ways to perform their experimental research more sustainably.

There are various aspects of sustainability in laboratory research that can and should be addressed: Besides enormous plastic waste generation by single-use products and energy consumption (especially by ultra-low temperature freezers as well as fume and sterile hoods) there is also massive water usage, for example for every 1l of deionized water 3l of fresh water are needed. Moreover, many of the consumables used in the lab have high environmental impact. Therefore, more conscious choices, for example aided by the ACT label [3], of products with less environmental impact and/or a production according to the principles of green chemistry are advised. Finally, there are various actions to improve sustainability in the IT regarding hardware (e.g. reduction in energy consumption by computers and computer screens) as well as sustainable data management (elimination of a so called “storage waste”).

It is clear that the excitement of the research community about sustainability is present and growing. However, the question remains how to maintain these changes in the long run. Many of the sustainability projects in the research institutes stem from grassroots initiatives (see [4]), including our own FMP Green Initiative initiated by the PhD students and postdocs of the department. This bottom-up approach by definition is deemed to be hard to sustain because there is a large rotation of researchers with non-permanent positions. Therefore, strong support from the permanent staff, both in leadership as well as technical positions, is required. One option is to undergo a certification process, for example through non-profit organizations such as My Green Lab or the LEAF program developed by University College London. In March 2021, our group was certified by My Green Lab with the highest, green level. Apart from the activities

mentioned above, there are other actions to sustain the movement: In case of the FMP Green Initiative, group members published a list of green guidelines for the lab, implemented a mandatory introductory “green lab tour”, as well as a yearly “green presentation” for the entire department to remind everyone about the guidelines and to discuss new challenges. These seemingly small actions in the long term will help to maintain the standards in the group as well as aid in raising awareness among other researchers.

The state of our planet calls for our actions right now. Therefore, volunteer-based grassroots organizations that start changes around their workspaces should grow and get support. However, in the long run, more systemic changes are needed: Support on the level of entire universities and research institutes or organizations (e.g. the Leibniz Association, the Max Planck Society), but also broader policy changes (see also LeNa Project [5]). Additionally, research funding should take into account gratifications for more sustainable actions, fund infrastructural changes, and support purchasing consumables that have a smaller environmental footprint but are more expensive. We wish that politics, funding agencies, and academics can work together to protect our planet and fulfill our duty to perform research in a socially responsible way. The GBM can help to spread the word and act as a melting pot to turn the various activities of individual groups and institutions into a movement!

References:

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